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DAMAGED LAND ON THE SOUTHERN ISLAND THE NEED FOR REKULTIVATION

Reyimov Nietbay Baynazarovich¹

Reyimov Omirbay Niyetbayevich²

Joldasbayeva Umida Jalgasbay kizi³

¹Karakalpak Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology, Head of the Department, Doctor of Agricultural Sciences, Associate Professor

²doctoral student at the Karakalpak Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

³student at the Karakalpak Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

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Abstract

Due to the fact that the area of degraded land in Karakalpakstan is increasing every year. In this case, land reclamation is of great importance in the return and restoration of agricultural land, and land reclamation must be carried out with high quality and strictly under control.

Keywords: Coast of the Aral Sea, Karakalpakstan, degraded, reclamation, saline soils, extreme climate, low water, stepped, terraced;

Introduction.

If we look at the condition of the lands of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the last 30-40 years, the main reasons for the increase in degraded lands are the extraction of minerals and fertilizers, brick factories, construction of highways and railways at various levels, water shortages, industrial development, rapid expansion of settlements, failure to rehabilitate lands that are decommissioned due to the drying up of perennial trees for various reasons, failure to develop quality land management projects, poor quality of most reclamation works. In order to return these decommissioned lands for use to the necessary sectors of the economy and to eliminate the negative impact of degraded lands on the environment, we must carry out reclamation work on these lands.

Although the Republic of Karakalpakstan is a republic rich in land resources within the Republic of Uzbekistan, land use here is not high. The reintroduction of decommissioned lands in the region to the national economy has not been done well. Therefore, reclamation works should be carried out in a systematic way to re-use decommissioned lands for national economic use, and reclamation works should be designed as an integral part of the technological process in the allocation of land for facilities whose activities lead to land degradation.

Research methodology.

As a result of our research work on the return of degraded lands to agricultural use or reclamation, the calculation and monitoring of degraded lands in the pilot plots of Takhtakupir district was divided into 4 categories and developed a sequence of agro-technical works.

The following materials were used in the development of the working project on land reclamation:

Guidelines for land reclamation:

- cutting, storage and rational use of fertile soil layer. Toshkent; ID-1255. 2018.
- Maps of lands of “Makpalkol” farm in Takhtakor district on the scale of 1: 10000, 1: 25000
- Engineering survey document for construction (MMC 01.07.97)
- Instructions for topographic survey.
- B.A. Dospekhov's methodology. 1985.

Land reclamation is a very complex activity. Therefore, its implementation requires the coordinated participation of a number of state authorities and local self-government bodies, as well as the coordinated participation and responsibility of the recipients of land rights. For effective reclamation, land plots, their implementers must have a certain degree of interest, or participate in this process as an individual (legal entity). Therefore, comparative analysis and monographic methods were widely used in our study.

Discussion.

The Rural Development Act of 1972, adopted in 1972, provides full authority and assistance in land status and use, soil fertility, water and other natural resources, and the publication of reports.

In 1977, the United States of America passed the Soil and Water Conservation Act. According to the law, at the suggestion and recommendation of officials of the Ministry of Agriculture and various government agencies, this year the country has conducted a full inventory and reclamation of all natural resources.

In most countries, reclamation work is carried out by various ministries and agencies. The Bureau of Land Management (BLM), a special unit of the U.S. Department of the Interior, organizes the inventory of federal lands and other natural resources. Under the 1976 Federal Land Policy and Land Management Act, reclamation is supported by the state. In this regard, the Bureau of Special Land Management has developed special land management and reclamation plans. All state landowners, local governments, the general public, landowners and land user groups, and producers involved in the development of these plans.

Research results.

The name of the activity specified in the plan of reclamation works is "Re-use of decommissioned irrigated lands". The average cost of re-use of decommissioned irrigated lands in Takhtakor district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan by category was calculated per 1 hectare, and the category of decommissioned lands was studied in 4 categories.

Including in 1 category - in good condition, it is possible to clean canals and ditches, to carry out drip irrigation, to clean canals, to use local hydrogels, to apply local fertilizers. The amount required per hectare is 36 million 726 thousand 582 soums.

Category 2 of degraded lands is low salinity per hectare of land, which can be harvested by cleaning canals and ditches, once drip irrigation after washing with salt, cleaning canals, using hydrogels and applying local fertilizers. 266 086 764 soums are required.

In the 3rd category of decommissioned lands, medium salinity, clearing of canals and collectors, cleaning of contours from bushes, cleaning of canals, application of hydrogels, drip irrigation after two saline washes, local fertilization, yield, available areas for 1 hectare The required amount amounted to 554,076,764 soums.

Category 4 of decommissioned lands includes areas with high salinity, laying power lines for pumping and transformer substations, clearing canals and collectors, filling the bottom of hectares of quarries, drip irrigation after three saline washes, and applying local fertilizers. The required amount for 1 hectare was 1 billion 23 million 222 thousand 764 soums.

Reclamation work can be done to use the land for various purposes and purposes, mainly in agriculture. The methods of using reclaimed land will depend on the natural and technical conditions in which they are located, economic and social needs, and economic interests.

Direction of reclamation In Takhtakor district, taking into account the engineering-geological structure of the pilot plots of Makpalkul, Uzbekistan, Mulik, Janadarya, N.Japakov and Takhtakopir massifs, taking into account the characteristics of the main land user and other factors, reclamation developed.

Conclusions.

1. Bringing land reclamation to the state level in the country, periodic holding of this event on all lands of the country, timely receipt of accurate quantitative and qualitative data on agricultural lands, including the return and restoration of arable land in agriculture, plays an important role in the existence

and continuous improvement as an important organizational measure in the search for the simplest ways to increase fertile land.

2. Degraded lands lose their economic value or drastically decrease in value. They are a source of soil, water and air pollution in neighboring areas, worsening the living conditions of the population. In order to return the degraded lands to use in various sectors of the economy and reduce their impact on the environment, it was necessary to carry out complex work on the restoration of degraded lands within the framework of the land allocation project.

3. On the basis of the above-mentioned working project, it can be noted that the following measures should be fully taken into account in the conditions of allocation of land plots allocated for the extraction of mineral resources;

- work on any land must fully meet the requirements of nature protection and environmental protection, reclamation;

- the requirements for ensuring the priority of agricultural lands, protection of lands from erosion, salinization, drying and rising groundwater levels, protection of water bodies, atmosphere (air) must be specified in land allocation agreements.

- consideration of the issue of rational use of land, restriction of land user rights, if necessary, taking into account the interests of the state and other land users, as well as land owners in case of violation of reclamation requirements. Only then can efficient use of lands and their protection be achieved.

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